

Detecting Abnormal Vehicle Movements and Accidents on Expressways Using Clustering Techniques

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Abstract: Vehicle detection and tracking is a core component in the area of traffic surveillance and management. Data collected in such observations can be used for generating useful information about traffic flows, vehicle counts, abnormal vehicle movements, accidents etc. In this paper, we present a method based on K-Means and spectral clustering to detect abnormal vehicle movements and accidents in videos recorded from the Surveillance cameras on Colombo-Katunayake Expressway (E03). The movement of vehicles are considered as events. The location trajectories of moving vehicles are considered as the feature trajectory. Foreground estimation and blob analysis are used on the video feed to generate the vehicle trajectories. Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) algorithm is used to measure the disparity between feature trajectories. The generated disparity matrix is used to create the normalized affinity matrix to eliminate disparity. Finally, eigenvectors of the Affinity matrix are calculated and the first largest K numbers of eigenvectors are considered for clustering. Further, K-Means Clustering is carried out to label the actual data. The study focuses on how clustering of real traffic video data can be used to determine abnormal traffic patterns and accidents on the expressways. The paper presents the algorithms and the test results with real world case studies. It is suggested that such systems can be used at the existing Colombo Katunayake Expressway monitoring Center to analyze the traffic surveillance videos.

Keywords: Traffic Event Analysis, Spectral Clustering, Event Detection, Image Processing

1. Introduction

Sri Lanka is undergoing major transportation infrastructure upgrades during the recent past. Newly built expressways in Sri Lanka contribute immensely to the economy and help hundreds of commuter easy passage between cities. Hence it is vital to assure the smooth operations of such expressways. This implies continuous video surveillance of the roads for useful data collection and monitoring for incidents that affect operations. Literature survey shows that intelligent transportations systems could effectively use computer vision and image processing-based vehicle tracking systems in order to collect vital information such as traffic flow patterns, abnormal vehicle movements on the lanes, accidents, traffic jams etc. [1-6].

The focus of our research is to show how the method presented in this paper could be utilized for traffic data collection on Colombo Katunayake expressway in Sri Lanka. The concerned Expressway is already installed with video surveillance system that covers the entire road network. Such information on traffic flow

and related incidents on the expressway may be very useful for RDA Engineers and stakeholders for designing, planning and future upgrades. Given the high volume of surveillance videos it might be tiresome for human observer, to gather useful information with naked eye continuously. This paper presents a method based on image processing and spectral clustering techniques to detect abnormal vehicle movement and accidents on Colombo Katunayake expressway. Also, it is shown how to interpret clustered data to understand the nature of traffic flow under various traffic conditions.

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The research work carried out may be considered to having two major parts. They are, motion pattern analysis and grouping of patterns based on similarities. The first step in motion pattern analysis is to extract the motion trajectories of moving object from the video source. For this purpose, image processing techniques such as foreground estimation, morphing and blob analysis may be used [7]. Once the trajectories are extracted similarity among the trajectories are tested and grouped using a suitable clustering algorithm.

Finding a suitable clustering algorithm has been the subject of many researches in previous works. Many of algorithms require a predefined number of clusters [8], [9] before they are able to group similar data. But in this type of real-world scenarios the actual number of clusters cannot be pre-determined. Hence the algorithm used for clustering should be capable of determining the number of clusters as well. The suitable algorithm with such capability for clustering motion trajectories was identified as Spectral Clustering [10], [11], [12]. Previous research works [13-17] show that real world motion trajectories may have large variations in motion trajectories. Hence A normalized Spectral Clustering Algorithm [18] is proven to be efficient to handle large variations of real-world trajectories of moving vehicles.

The paper presents the overview of the method in Section 2. Image processing techniques and the spectral clustering algorithm are presented in Section 3 and 4. Section 5 presents the clustering results for four cases from Colombo Katunayake Expressway surveillance videos. The paper concludes with Section 6.

2. Overview of the method

Figure 1 shows the important steps involved in the proposed method. The parameters used in Morphological Operation and Blob Analysis will change how the trajectories are extracted. Such parameters may be considered as variables that change based on the video source. Once trajectories are obtained, Dynamic Time Warping algorithm is used to generate a similarity matrix of the trajectories which is used as the base for spectral clustering algorithm. Finally, K-means Clustering is used to label the actual data and detect the abnormal events.

Figure 1 - Overview of the Method

3. Motion Trajectory Extraction

The first step in motion pattern analysis is to extract motion trajectories of the concerned objects from the video source. The first step is to use a suitable foreground and background estimation method in order to distinguish the moving vehicles from the background. In this research, a background removal algorithm based on Gaussian mixture models [19] is used. By applying proper morphological operations on the binary frame, spurious detections due to noise can be reduced. In order to detect moving objects, a blob analysis is done for each frame. Blob analysis detects connected pixels which mostly correspond to moving objects. In order to predict the connected pixels correctly that correspond to the same blob in each frame, Kalman filter is applied to each frame. Then trajectories are generated by tracking the $\{X, Y\}$ coordinates of the centroids of the detected blobs [20].

The practical challenges faced during trajectory extraction was avoiding detection of noisy blobs that are detected due to non-vehicle movements captured on the camera. In order to minimize such noise blob tuning was carried out and suitable blob size was chosen [21]. Blob size for vehicles on different video sources was experimentally chosen as vehicle sizes in the video varied based on the camera focus and distance from camera. Figure 2 shows how vehicles are detected and assigned with unique ID for identification. Figure 3 shows same frame where the background is removed and only the detected blobs of moving objects are shown. The trajectories of detected vehicles are extracted as shown in Figure 4.

4. Feature Trajectory Analysis and Clustering

Motion trajectories of vehicles extracted from the video may be of various lengths. In order to compare varying length feature trajectories an algorithm called Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [22] is used. DTW compares two trajectories by considering the shape and direction. Such information is used to generate a disparity matrix which is used by the spectral clustering algorithm.

Figure 2 - Detecting vehicles based on blob size and assigning unique ID number

Figure 3 - Vehicles after background removal

Figure 4 - Extracted Trajectories of vehicles

A set of trajectories, $T = \{T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_n\}$ in R^n extracted from the video source can be modeled as a closed network by denoting in a disparity matrix D as in,

$$D_{i,j} = \text{Distance}(T_i, T_j), \quad \dots(1)$$

Where $\text{Distance}(T_i, T_j)$ denotes the DTW optimal cost between the i^{th} trajectory (T_i) and j^{th} trajectory (T_j).

When comparing real world expressway videos, it was noted that many short noisy trajectories were generated due to camera movement, merge and split of vehicles. Such noisy trajectories are unavoidable but can be minimized by doing proper morphological operation and selecting suitable blob size for detecting vehicles.

4.1 Spectral Clustering Algorithm

Different implementations of spectrum clustering algorithms are available. In this research a version mentioned in [18] is implemented. The method classifies the original data into K groups by clustering the eigen vectors derived from the original data. The steps of the algorithm implemented is as following:

- Compute the Affinity matrix $A \in R^{n \times n}$, for the data set using the transformation,

$$A_{ij} = \exp \left\{ -\frac{D_{i,j}^2}{2\sigma^2} \right\} \text{ if } i \neq j \text{ and } A_{i,i} = 0, \dots(2)$$

where σ (sigma) is a **tunable** parameter.

- Form the Laplacian L as following

$$L = N_A^{-1/2} A N_A^{-1/2} \quad \dots (3)$$

N_A defined as the diagonal matrix whose $(i,i)^{th}$ element is the sum of A 's i^{th} row.

- Apply eigenvalue decomposition to matrix L and form matrix X by stacking the eigenvectors corresponding to the largest k eigenvalues. k is the position where largest eigengap is detected. X is given as,

$$X = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n] \in R^{n \times k} \quad \dots (4)$$

- Form matrix Y by normalizing each row of matrix X to have a unit length as following,

$$Y_{i,j} = \frac{x_{i,j}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^k x_{i,j}^2}} \quad \dots (5)$$

- Finally, the rows of Y are clustered into K clusters by treating each row of Y as a feature vector for the original data. Then original trajectories are assigned to the K clusters using the K-Means algorithm.

4.1 Setting the Tunable Parameter (σ)

Previous works suggest that by varying the σ value it is possible to fine tune the clusters for real world cases [23]. In this research rather than focusing on single σ value multiple values for σ was tested in order to detect the accurate clusters and sub clusters since in real world the trajectories may be overlapping [18]. The value of $\sigma = 0.4$ was pre-selected experimentally and was passed as a predefined value to the algorithm.

5. Test Results

In order to test the practicality and accuracy of the system, the method was applied on real world traffic surveillance videos taken from Colombo Katunayake Expressway. Four different case studies were chosen and the clustering results for each case study are presented. Each group of clusters is marked by different color and symbol for identification.

5.1 Case 1 -Normal Traffic Flow

During a normal traffic flow, vehicles are expected to drive along the designated lanes. Naturally this would form clusters based on number of lanes where movement is detected.

As shown in Figure 5, three distinct clusters were formed along the lanes where vehicle movements were detected.

5.2 Case 2-High Volume Traffic flow

Detecting clusters when traffic volume is higher poses few challenges. Two vehicles travelling on same direction same speed may be detected as single blob. When such vehicles change speed or change lane it may cause short trajectories being formed due the merge and split of blobs.

Figure 5 - Three distinct clusters formed along the three lanes

Keeping small blob size detects more vehicles but tendency for noise increases. The most ideal value for blob size may vary depending on the video focus area, angle, camera tilt and noise level on video. Figure 6, Figure 7 show same video source, analyzed with two different blobs sizes. It can be seen larger blob size reduces noise and forms the clusters properly. Hence, proper blob size was also selected experimentally based on blob analysis.

Figure 6 -Two clusters formed along the lanes with significant noise (Blob size = 300)

5.3 Case 3-Detecting Accident

When accidents occur on the Expressway there is a high possibility the vehicle(s) involved in the accident will cause an abnormality on the normal traffic flow. Trajectories of such vehicles will be short and scattered around the scene of incident. Such trajectories will tend to form a separate cluster among themselves. Figure 8 shows how only two clusters are formed when traffic is normal. Figure 9 shows new cluster formed when accident occurred on left lane.

Figure 7 - Two clusters formed along the lanes with less noise (Blob size = 900)

Figure 8 - Two clusters formed when traffic flow is normal

Figure 9 - Abnormal cluster formed on left lane due to a vehicle involved in an accident

5.4 Case 4-Detecting Abnormal Movement

Abnormal movements may be a vehicle moving on the wrong direction on a certain lane. For this study movement of a maintenance vehicle moving on reverse direction was considered. Figure 10 shows how two clusters formed when traffic only occurred on designated lanes and Figure 11 shows how third cluster is formed when the abnormal reverse movement is detected.

Figure 10 - Two clusters formed along normal vehicle flow

Figure 11 - The maintenance vehicle is detected as separate cluster as it's moving on (reverse) wrong direction

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a methodology to detect abnormal vehicle movements and accidents from surveillance video streams. To evaluate the performance of the model real world surveillance videos from Colombo Katunayake Expressway were analyzed. It is demonstrated via different case studied that the proposed method is successfully able to detect abnormal movement and accidents on the Expressway. It is also suggested that this method could be used to analyze traffic patterns on other Expressways in Sri Lanka.

Figure 12 – (a) Cluster space for Figure 5; (b) Cluster space for Figure 7; (c) Cluster space for Figure 8; (d) Cluster Space for Figure 9.

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References

1. H. Chung-Lin and L. Wen-Chieh, "A vision-based vehicle identification system," in *Pattern Recognition, 2004. ICPR 2004. Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on*, 2004, pp. 364- 367 Vol.4.
2. Z. Wei, et al., "Multilevel Framework to Detect and Handle Vehicle Occlusion," *Intelligent Transportation Systems, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 9, pp. 161-174, 2008.
3. N. K. Kanhere and S. T. Birchfield, "Real-Time Incremental Segmentation and Tracking of Vehicles at Low Camera Angles Using Stable Features," *Intelligent Transportation Systems, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 9, pp. 148-160, 2008.
4. G. T. Bae, S. Y. Kwak, and H. R. Byun, "Motion pattern analysis using partial trajectories for abnormal movement detection in crowded scenes," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 186-187, Jan 2013.
5. W. Hu, X. Xiao, D. Xie, T. Tan, S. Maybank. *Traffic Accident Prediction Using 3-D Model-Based Vehicle Tracking*. In *Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, IEEE Vol. 53, No 3, pp. 677-694, May 2004.
6. M. Kimachi, K. Kanayama, K. Teramoto. *Incident Prediction by Fuzzy Image Sequence Analysis*. In *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Vehicle Navigation and Information Systems (VNIS' 94)*, pp. 51-57, 1994.
7. W. S. K. Fernando, H. M. S. P. B. Herath, P. H. Perera, M. P. B. Ekanayake, G. M. R. I. Godaliyadda and J. V. Wijayakulasooriya, "Object identification, enhancement and tracking under dynamic background conditions," *7th International Conference*

- on Information and Automation for Sustainability, Colombo, 2014, pp. 1-6.
8. T. Kanungo, D. M. Mount, N. S. Netanyahu, C. D. Piatko, R. Silverman, and A. Y. Wu, "An efficient k-means clustering algorithm: Analysis and implementation," *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 881-892, 2002.
 9. F. Jiang, Y. Wu, and A. K. Katsaggelos, "A dynamic hierarchical clustering method for trajectory-based unusual video event detection," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 907-913, April 2009.
 10. U. Von Luxburg, "A tutorial on spectral clustering," *Statistics and computing*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 395-416, 2007.
 11. C. C. Aggarwal and C. K. Reddy, *Data clustering: algorithms and applications*. CRC Press, 2013.
 12. R. A. A. Rupasinghe, S. G. M. P. Senanayake, D. A. Padmasiri, M. P. B. Ekanayake, G. M. R. I. Godaliyadda, and J. V. Wijayakulasooriya, "MOTION PATTERN ANALYSIS IN VIDEO STREAMS BASED ON SPECTRAL CLUSTERING", *Proceedings of the Peradeniya University International Research Sessions, Sri Lanka, Vol. 20, pp. 62, 04th & 5th November 2016*
 13. H. Li, A. Achim, and D. Bull, "Unsupervised video anomaly detection using feature clustering," *IET signal processing*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 521-533, 2012.
 14. F. Porikli and T. Haga, "Event detection by eigenvector decomposition using object and frame features," in *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshop, 2004. CVPRW'04. Conference on. IEEE, 2004*, pp. 114-114.
 15. U. V. Luxburg, O. Bousquet, and M. Belkin, "Limits of spectral clustering," in *Advances in neural information processing systems, 2004*, pp. 857-864.
 16. W. Y. Chen, Y. Song, H. Bai, C. J. Lin, and E. Y. Chang, "Parallel spectral clustering in distributed systems," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 568-586, March 2011.
 17. H. M. S. P. B. Herath, P. H. Perera, M. P. B. Ekanayake, and G. M. R. I. Godaliyadda, "Visual event classification with human like perception," in *2015 IEEE 10th International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems (ICIIS)*, Dec 2015, pp. 378-383.
 18. A. Y. Ng, M. I. Jordan, Y. Weiss et al., "On spectral clustering: Analysis and an algorithm," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 2, pp. 849-856, 2002
 19. "Human action segmentation and recognition via motion and shape analysis," *Pattern Recognition Letters*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 438 - 445, 2012, *intelligent Multimedia Interactivity*.
 20. H. M. S. P. B. Herath, P. H. Perera, W. S. K. Fernando, M. P. B. Ekanayake, G. M. R. I. Godaliyadda, and J. V. Wijayakulasooriya, "Human motion tracking under dynamic background conditions," in *2014 9th International Conference on Industrial and Information Systems (ICIIS)*, Dec 2014, pp. 1-6.
 21. S.G.M.P. Senanayake, R.A.A. Rupasinghe, D.A. Padmasiri, M.P.B. Ekanayake, G.M.R.I. Godaliyadda, and J.V. Wijayakulasooriya, "Trajectory Refinement Using an Adaptive Filtering Method for Event Detection and Classification", *Annual Sessions of IESL*, pp. 415-422, 2016
 22. M. Muller, "Dynamic time warping," *Information retrieval for music and motion*, pp. 69-84, 2007.
 23. R. A. A. Rupasinghe, S. G. M. P. Senanayake, D. A. Padmasiri, M. P. B. Ekanayake, G. M. R. I. Godaliyadda and J. V. Wijayakulasooriya, "Modes of clustering for motion pattern analysis in video surveillance," *2016 IEEE International Conference on Information and Automation for Sustainability (ICIAfS)*, Galle, pp. 1-6, 2016.

